

Master's Thesis On

MARKETING STRATEGIES AND BRANDING OF PAYTM

***FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF
MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION***

**UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF
Dr. /Prof. Anam Khan**

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School of Business

Galgotias University

May, 2022

**School of Business
Galgotias University**

Certificate

This is to certify that the Master's Thesis "*Marketing strategies Of Phonepe E-Wallet*" has been prepared by Mr./Ms. under my supervision and guidance. The project report is submitted towards the partial fulfillment of 2 year, Full time Master of Business Administration.

Name & Signature of Faculty

Date

Declaration

I, **Revati Kumari** Roll No.(**20GSOB201049**) student of School of Business, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, hereby declare that the Master's Thesis on "*Marketing strategies Of Phonepe E-Wallet*" is an original and authenticated work done by me.

I further declare that it has not been submitted elsewhere by any other person in any of the institutes for the award of any degree or diploma.

Revati Kumari (20GSOB2010149)

Date 08/05/2022

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I would like to give warmest gratefulness to my faculty mentor and supervisor **Dr./Prof. Himanshi Gaur** for bringing the weight of his considerable experience and knowledge to this research work named "**Marketing strategies Of Phonepe E-Wallet**". Her continuous guidance and fetching out the most relevant and practical topic for the research so that I can grind my own knowledge. I perceive as this opportunity as a big milestone in my career development. I will strive to use gained skills and knowledge in the best possible way, and I will continue to work on their improvement, in order to attain desired career objectives. Hope to continue cooperation with good people in future. As we have come to our end journey of being a professional course, this project will add on more value to my professional life coming ahead. This research work will emphasis towards the current scenario of the market and polish my understanding of various issues and problems faced by general public. I will make sure to gain that learning in this project that will enhance my knowledge and area of specialization.

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Introduction

The rapid rise in the growth of mobile technology throughout the world is a phenomenon that has been particularly remarkable among poor people, largely because of the prepaid model. As a result, all classes of society now have access to financial services as people become increasingly familiar with a mobile-money system.

In fact, mobile technology, viewed as a payment or banking channel, has the potential to allow two important questions to be addressed at the same time: on the demand side, it represents an opportunity for financial inclusion among a population that is underserved by traditional banking services. On the supply side, it opens up possibilities for financial institutions to deliver a great diversity of services at low cost to a large clientele of the poorest sections of society and people living in remote areas.

Although there are more than 120 mobile money projects being undertaken in about 70 emerging markets (Beshouri et al. 2010), mobile payment has only become a normal practice in a few countries, despite its huge potential. The lack of worldwide dissemination of a service with such a huge potential shows that successful cases are not clearly understood, and as a consequence, are not being easily replicated. This suggests that lessons are not being learnt from the places where the system has been successfully adopted. Furthermore, we suspect that the obstacles to its adoption in most countries are not being investigated deeply enough to allow implementation strategies to be employed on the basis of reliable business models. If these issues can be clarified, the potential social and economic impacts of mobile money can be more

effectively measured and this can persuade policy-makers to create favourable regulatory environments for fostering the practice of digital payments.

In view of the importance of mobile money and payment initiatives, and the gaps in the current state of knowledge in the field, the objective of this paper is to provide a knowledge base on mobile money, based on a comprehensive literature review, and can be employed to identify significant experiences, together with the models being deployed around the world, especially in developing countries. Although there are literature reviews currently available both in the general context of mobile payment (Dahlberg et al., 2008) and in the field of mobile financing in developing countries (Duncombe and Boateng, 2009), the present work focuses on mobile payment/mobile money (as opposed to mobile financing in general) with a special stress on local

development (but not limited to works that deal with development or developing countries). This article also updates and substantially expands the existing literature reviews on the subject. While Dahlberg et al. analysed 73 peer-reviewed papers, and Duncombe and Boateng reviewed 43 research papers (17 peer-reviewed and 23 non-peer-reviewed), the present review examines a total of 196 papers (94 peer-reviewed and 92 non-peer-reviewed) published between 2001 and 2011.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the theoretical background for this paper; Section 3 describes the methodology employed. Following this, the results are analysed in Section 4. Lastly, Section 5 discusses the results and makes some concluding remarks for the paper.

Research Objective

The focus of this research is to identify the trends in the newly rising Ewallet industry and find reasons that affect the usage pattern of the consumers.

- 1) To understand the E-wallet market in India and its growth in India in recent years.
- 2) To identify and understand factors affecting choice of E-wallet and its consumer preferences.
- 3) To conduct a comparative study of prominent E-wallets in India.

Literature Review

In this study, the discussion about this report contains the basic introduction about both of the organizations “ Marketing strategies Of Phonepe E-Wallet.

Chawla (2019) collected data from 744 respondents and discovered that trust, easy to use and security have an effect on the attitude of consumers to use e-wallets. Girija (2019) collected data from 150 respondents and revealed that cash back offers and convenience are the main reasons to use ewallets. Senthil (2019) surveyed 150 respondents and found that users are satisfied with Paytm services as it resolves the problem within 24 hours. Sivakumar and Balaji (2019) got responses from 100 respondents and discovered that there is no significant relationship between age and use of Paytm.

FE Bureau (2017) states that According to the RBI: Demonetization has increased the growth of Paytm & Mobi Kwik which is known as the Digital payment companies. “A Newspaper Article in Financial Express”.

Dr. Poonam Painuly, Shalu Rathi in their paper “Mobile Wallet: An upcoming mode of business transactions” (May 2016) clearly explains about the mobile wallet, it’s types and latest trends. At that point examined about Role of portable wallet in different divisions like Banks, Retail and Hospitality. The paper clarifies the significance of versatile wallet for Banks, Customers and Companies. In future extension it also discusses on the versatile wallets turning into a trend of advertising channel in not so distant future. Also, contributing exceedingly in a consistent shopping knowledge for the clients that expansion their inclination for regular and more repurchases with delightful encounters. They additionally talk on the significance and development of portable cash in business, social and monetary planned. The nearness of versatile wallet spreading from urban to country territories on a huge scale. Henceforth, wallet cash sees a high splendid future in close time.

Prof Trilok Nath Shukla in his paper “Mobile Wallet: Present and the Future” (June 2016) has discussed about mobile wallet, working, types and its advantages and disadvantages. His analysis included perception of consumers and retailers about mobile wallets. He concluded that mobile wallets will be

used to engage with the customer by the marketers and digital businesses. Irrespective of the market status of these mobile wallets, marketers should take advantage of the emerging opportunities.

Key Pousttchi and Dietmar G. Wiedemann in their paper “What Influences Consumers’ Intention to Use Mobile Payments?” (2008) studied the adoption of mobile payments and evaluated what key influences affected consumers to use mobile payments and found that subjective security was not a primary driver of mobile payment acceptance. They found that perceived confidentiality of payment details and perceived trustworthiness were strongly correlated. Four key variables were found to directly impacting consumer intention and usage behavior: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions.

Myersin (1969) stated that the vast majority of the innovation are essentially advertise driven and is acquainted as an answer with the particular needs of the customer. Lynn (1966) states that more development is presented in Consumer Market when contrasted with mechanical markets. Galbraith (1970).

Phonepe E-Wallet

PhonePe has been leading the industry in all key metrics including number and number of jobs, registered users and vendor inclusion. The first to be a market leader in the UPI with a market share of over 46% in the volume of activities considered last year.

PhonePe Transaction Value In CY21

Benefits a of Phonepe

- . Fast and easy recharge.
- . A problem-free payment to the Seller.
- . Easy Bill Payment Kanye Autopay.
- . UPI Fund Transfer.
- . One app for many services.
- . Slightly Secure (Does not require a PIN or password to unlock)
- . Delay in payment.
- . Non-Credit of Money.

Research Methodology

The aim of this research paper is to analyze the usage of PayTm by users. In order to reach the aim a structured questionnaire was sent to 230 smart phone users who use PayTm for online payment. The respondents were categorized on the basis of, age, Frequency of usage, Purpose of usage and average monthly spending on PayTm. Out of 230 people only 151 responded to the questionnaire. This research used descriptive method in order to get the statistic result from respondents.

Sample design: -. The study is done by using Convenience sampling method with 95% confidence and 5% margin of error. A sample of 50 employees have been taken across India. The data gathered was analyzed using Percentage Analysis, Correlation Test and Chi-square Test.

☑ Data Collection: In view of this questionnaires were sent to 50 respondents and the inquiries were asked where their responses are noted. Respondents are mainly college students, employed and non-employed youths, middle aged people both employed and non-employed and the merchants.

☑ Data Analysis Tool: Microsoft Excel program.

The research methodology used is explorative study which includes primary data and secondary data.

The sample size chose are 20 customers of Pay U Money and Pay tm which constitutes 20 customers belonging to 18-30. Our survey is based on questionnaire method.

● Awareness about Phonepe or Payu Money-

Pay tm or Pay u Money refers to the electronic payment for online transactions which offers recharges, shopping, utility bill payments etc. Nowadays, people are aware about various services provided by pay tm or pay u money. It catches the attention of young customers as it gets noticed by working on unique ads. As this brand is increased day by day by the people it has created 100% awareness about the pay tm or pay u money by both the age groups and agreed about various facilities provided by it.

Table 1: depicts the customers opinion regarding Pay TM and Pay U Money

Sl.no.	Particulars	Age group (18 to 30) years		Age group (30 to 45) years	
		Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
1.	Awareness about Pay tm or Pay u Money	100%	0%	100%	0%
2.	Any delay in payment	40%	60%	80%	20%
3.	Security system	60%	40%	100%	0%
4.	Problems encountered while making payment	70%	30%	60%	40%
5.	Problem solving:				
	• Refund to A/c	40%	0%	60%	0%
	• Refund to wallet	60%	0%	40%	0%
6.	Satisfied with coupons, cash back and offers	85%	15%	80%	20%
7.	Satisfied with Pay tm or Pay u Money	100%	0%	100%	0%

Chart 1: showing users opinion about Paytm and Pay U Money (b/w age group 18-30)

● **Any delay in payment-**

Pay tm have the option of recharging and shopping from whenever, anywhere and access from wherever they are. Before opting, pay tm people should think twice or not whether they provide service. Pay tm plays a significant role in payment of online transactions, but they suffer from the technological barriers as server may busy. According to the survey, it shows greater volume for positive i.e. 60% people have agreed that there is no delay in payment and 40% people have disagreed between 18 to 30 years. Even there is a positive reaction in 30 to 45 years, as 80% people agreed and 20% people disagreed. The disagreed people have told about that they have recharge mobile for Rs.100 but for 40-45 min it did not process and did not refund to bank a/c. this error was due to technical fault in pay tm. Pay tm have the option of recharging and shopping from whenever, anywhere and access from wherever they are. Before opting, pay tm people should think twice or not whether they provide service. Pay tm plays a significant role in payment

of online transactions, but they suffer from the technological barriers as server may busy. According to the survey, it shows greater volume for positive i.e. 60% people have agreed that there is no delay in payment and 40% people have disagreed between 18 to 30 years. Even there is a positive reaction in 30 to 45 years, as 80% people agreed and 20% people disagreed. The disagreed people have told about that they have recharge mobile for Rs.100 but for 40-45 min it did not process and did not refund to bank a/c. this error was due to technical fault in pay tm.

- **Security system**

Nowadays, pay tm offers advanced account protection to gain this we have to login to additional layer of security on pay tm website. Pay tm has designed 2 step authentications to keep safe and secure our pay tm in mobile applications.

This feature is to make sure our account safe always. As the security system is available to all in advanced way, people are well known about the attractive security training; majority of people i.e. 100% have satisfied with this between 30-40 years. Meanwhile, between 18-30 years' age group 16 people are agreed and 4 people are disagreed because all of them are vulnerable to password thefts. To secure our pay tm transactions, we tend to use same password on all platforms and websites for our convenience.

- **Problems encountered while making payments**

Pay tm strongly believes in a sincere and transparent approach to its users. Pay tm treats the users fairly all times and encounter the problems and they take care of all complaints effectively. As the main aim of pay tm is at minimising customer complaints, grievances and reviews and

redressal as they give first preference to customers to solve their problems. All the employees at pay tm works in a good faith and people are attracted towards this pay tm or Pay u money application 15 people of them are agreed and 5 people are disagreed in 18-30 years of age group. As well, complaints raised by users are dealt with an open mind with courtesy and in timely manner most of them are satisfied nearly 6 of them agreed and 4 of them disagreed between 30-45 years' age group.

- **Problem solving: Refund to A/c, Refund to wallet, no refund**

For every problem, there is a solution. Here also pay tm users will come across some of the problems like delay in service, refundable etc. at the same time they also provide solutions to the customer problems. Pay tm solve the problems by refunding their amount to their A/c or to the wallet. Sometimes it may not refund also. According to the survey, the amount has been refund to their wallet is high than refund to their a/c for the 18-30 years' age group. The amount that has been refund to their wallet is 16, and refund to their a/c is 4. But for the 30-45 years' age group users have received their amount to their a/c is high i.e. 6 than compare to refund to their wallet is 4. So, pay tm app has provided these types of solutions as the users are increasing day by day.

- **Satisfied with coupons, cash backs and offers**

Pay tm not only process quick online transactions for payments of recharge, utility bill payments etc. it also provides various offers like coupons, cash backs etc. recently pay tm is giving special offer as if we make payment for Rs 100 using our pay tm wallet we will get Rs 105 cash back within 5-6 min as it will be valid for only 2 coupons. As it provides various offers it is attracted

by all the users. Special offers, coupons, cash backs etc offered by pay tm plays a major role. As in today's world people foresee about the various attractive gifts and keen to get benefit from one thing. As per this majority of people i.e. 17 are satisfied and 3 are unsatisfied between 18-30 years of age group. And also between 30-45 years 8 people are satisfied and 2 people are unsatisfied.

- **Satisfied with Phonepe or PayU money**

Pay tm mainly focus on payment of online transactions, DTH recharge, utility bill payments. It provides true, accurate and complete information about pay tm or pay u money. It acts as a pivotal role as we can pay through debit card, credit card, net banking. It also provides security system to safeguard our wallet balance and it also offers cash backs, discount vouchers etc. Though it has been introduced recently people are well known about this and satisfied in processing it. Nowadays world is growing at large, they provide various applications to make online payments i.e. Pay tm, Pay u Money, net banking etc. Based on the users, pay tm or pay u money creating a new brand in the society. According to the survey in both the age groups i.e. 18-30 years and 30-45 years' age group people gave their 100% satisfaction towards pay tm but they have a request to get quick payment of transactions to benefit more to them.

DATA ANALYSIS

Digital Transformation is far beyond just moving from traditional banking to a digital world. It is a vital change in how banks and other financial institutions learn about, interact with and satisfy customers. An efficacious Digital Transformation begins with an understanding of digital customer behavior, preferences, choices, likes, dislikes, stated as well as unstated needs, aspirations etc. And this transformation leads to the major changes in the organizations, from product-centric to customer-centric view.

A study by CGI entitled, Understanding Financial Consumers in the Digital Era sheds some light on the desires of today's digital consumer. Interestingly, at a time when financial institutions seem to be in a lock-step with each other, consumers are raising the bar on their expectations. And, according to the study by CGI, they are willing to leave where they currently bank if their needs are not met.

The most effective way to understand and bring the organization from traditional banking to digital banking is Omni-Channel approach. Omni-channel is a multichannel approach to customer service where all the channels are tightly integrated, keeping customer in the centre of the integration. As customers continue to change their channel usage patterns, banks and credit firms need to focus on delivering a seamless customer experience across various touch points. More than just an axiom, Omni-channel banking is a prospect to take bottom-line on higher note by gaining insights from customers' channels, behavior and preferences. Today's customers are more sophisticated and tech savvy, and to cater to their specific needs, each customer needs a unique experience from banking. They want the companies to understand their unstated needs as well as their likes. So, it should come as no surprise that these customers are expecting similar kind of response and service from banking institutions too. From researching new services, opening an account, checking balance, conducting transactions, loans, credits, wealth management, customer support, delivering an Omni-channel experience has become a key to success in this competitive marketplace.

In the current multichannel model, customers are directed to the least expensive channel which grounds to not only the dissatisfaction, but also the channel hopping. The whole process is inefficient, costly and inconsistent. Omni-channel is not the replacement of multichannel, but it's the enrichment. Espousal of Omni-channel is indispensable to ensure that customer experience is unified, incorporated and supports customer at the right time, in the right place as the right way. It must be as per their mobile and digital life style. Staying germane in current banking revolution entails deep acquaintance of customers' needs, wants and demands. It also requires the precise

mixture of IT infrastructure and innovative new technologies to certify that one remains ahead in current market space to drive top, as well as bottom lines upwards.

Few statistics on the future of customer engagement:

- 73% of marketers view customer centricity as critical to the success of their business and role at the company. (The CMO Council, Mastering Adaptive Customer Engagement 2014)
- 70% of buying experiences are based on how the customer feels they are being treated. (McKinsey)
- A 2% increase in customer retention has the same effect as decreasing costs by 10%. (Leading on the Edge of Chaos, Emmet Murphy and Mark Murphy)
- In the retail banking industry, customers who are fully engaged bring 37% more annual revenue to their primary bank than do customers who are actively disengaged. (Gallup State of the American Consumer 2014)
- Fully engaged policy owners purchase 22% more types of insurance products than actively disengaged policy owners. (Gallup State of the American Consumer 2014)
- The majority of businesses are unable to support an Omni-channel customer journey. (Forrester Wave Customer Service Solutions 2014) • Only 12% can provide a seamless hand-off between channels. (Forrester Wave Customer Service Solutions 2014).

Recommendations/Suggestions

- Bank should ask consumer feedback regularly to know the extent of consumer's satisfaction with the service and product of the company. If they are dissatisfied, then the reasons for dissatisfaction should be found out and should be corrected.
- Company should adopt effective promotional strategies to increase the awareness level among the consumers.
- Since customer's satisfaction is the key to success, the Company should increase its brand image through improvement performance and services to the customer's satisfaction.
- With regard to E commerce products and services, consumers respond at different rates, depending on the consumer's characteristics. Hence, Phonepe Company should try to bring their new product and services to the attention of potential early customers.
- Due to intense competition in the financial market, Phonepe Company should adopt strategies to attract more customers.
- As there is intense competition, Phonepe Company should work hard to maintain its position and offer better service and products to consumers for future expansions.

- Majority of the people find banking and online business important in their life, so the company should employ the strategies to convert the want in to need which will enrich E commerce business.

Discussion and Conclusion

This paper has extensively analysed academic and non-academic papers related to the important topic of mobile money. After searching significant sources to identify who (researchers and institutions) is publishing what (the related topics) and where (the countries studied, journals and databases), this paper has attempted to provide a comprehensive picture of the knowledge production and dissemination of mobile for payments around the world.

By examining peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed papers from relevant academic and non-academic sources, we sought for information related to mobile money and payment that could help us to understand the following dimensions: the interactions between the different actors involved in these initiatives; the factors that impeded or encouraged their adoption; the main services delivered; the effects on local flows of money; legal and regulatory environments as well as the role of authorities; and related issues of gender behavior.

Although a fairly extensive search was carried out on almost two hundred papers, which can be

considered to be very representative of the publications on mobile money and payment, we found that little attention had been paid to the dimensions we searched for. This gap in the literature helps to explain why a service with such a huge potential has not been disseminated worldwide. This failure includes the following factors: the fact that successful cases are not clearly understood, and as a result, are not being easily replicated; the problem that obstacles and unsuccessful cases are, in most countries, not being investigated in sufficient depth to allow implementation strategies to be based on reliable business models; and the fact that the potential social and economic effects are not being assessed properly with the result that the policy makers are not convinced of the need to invest heavily in fostering favorable regulatory environments for digital payment.

At the same time, the literature review revealed the most important issues currently being investigated by specialists in the field with regard to mobile money and payment, and thus allowed us to understand the main contribution they can make to this area of study. This information can act as a starting-point for drawing up a research agenda that can be adopted by academics, policy makers and practitioners concerned with the subject of mobile payments.

Furthermore, some clear gaps in our knowledge of mobile payments were discovered by the research and analysis. Some of these gaps represent important issues that can be explored in future research in the field. Similarly to Buncombe and Boating (2009), the present literature review confirms the same gaps pointed to by those authors (geographical, methodological and conceptual), even analyzing a more comprehensive sample. It was confirmed the existence of an important theoretical gap related to the central themes of study in the analyzed articles: an expressive portion of them focuses on issues such as adoption or market analysis, neglecting

other relevant themes, such as regulation and effective socio-economic impacts. Even among the studies focused on consumer adoption, there is a significant concentration on a few theories: many of them use theoretical models like TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) and its variations, aiming to identify the factors that may influence the adoption of mobile money and payment, denoting another theoretical gap.

In addition, the studies are concentrated in a few cases/countries, with emphasis on Kenya and the Philippines, although there are experiences in dozens of other countries (Bistoury et al. 2010). Thus, an important geographic gap is evidenced, because although there are emerging mobile money/payments initiatives worldwide, academic and non-academic production does not cover them adequately, as is the case of emerging initiatives in Latin American countries. On the peer-reviewed papers side, this situation might be attributed to the relative absence of Latin American researchers in the mainstream of academic journals, which are largely dominated by researchers from developed countries. On the other hand, the emergence of studies in Africa and Asia is a striking feature and suggests that the experiences in these countries have attracted more interest from researchers in developed countries. As other non-academic research institutions and consultancy firms have embarked on their publishing activities on this subject later than the academic institutions, the influence of such cases in Africa, for example, has become dominant. The low economic and social importance attached to mobile payment experiences in the region – such as the case of Daviplata, in Colombia and Paggo, in Brazil, for example – might also be related to the limited ability of banks, MNOs and regulators to understand regional peculiarities concerning mobile payment models. This situation opens up opportunities for researchers to turn their attention to this issue and carry out in-depth investigations in the region.

As an example of track research that can also be followed by researchers, current experiences of financial inclusion can point to correspondent banking networks, which had been successful in developing alternative payment channels for the poor in countries like Brazil, Colombia and Peru, for example, long before mobile payment models became a part of the international agenda (Denis et. al. 2011; Mas 2009; Kumar et. al. 2006). Although different in many ways from one another, the correspondent and mobile payment systems require a complex web of relationships among a wide range of actors to deliver financial services to an underserved part of the population, which is at the same time supported by a strong regulatory environment. Understanding the process of building such a complex network of relationships could be helpful to mobile money researchers in at least two ways: first to encourage an analysis to be conducted of the actors' interactions that made it possible for this complex network to grow in countries in the region; and second to seek opportunities to include the use of mobile devices in the correspondent model, since it is still based on a system of cash payments, which is clearly an inefficient method that must be superseded.

Another important gap that was identified in the published literature related to mobile money is the relative absence of an analysis of the economic or social impact. Most studies, in particular non-academic ones, take social and economic impacts for granted or just give them a cursory mention, without further investigation or corroborative analysis. To improve research in this area,

studies related to microfinance could be inspirational, since in this field the emergence of randomized studies and other techniques have led to this system being widely adopted. This

follows many years of numerous superficial investigations but few in-depth research-based studies that can be used to provide evidence of the real impact of microfinance practices on alleviating poverty at micro (household), meso (community) and macro (regional or country) levels. It is understandable that the effects of these studies in social sciences are still to be felt, in view of the unsuitable conditions for carrying out experiments and isolating variables (because of the sheer number involved and the difficulty of making precise measurements) in order to make comparisons, either geographically or over a period of time. Despite the challenge, it is essential for this area of studies to be sponsored by research institutions.

Among the many questions in the area of mobile payment studies that require answers, the following should be highlighted: the typology of business models, the legal issues involved in the implementations (whether successful or unsuccessful), the kinds of technology associated with the particular business models adopted, cultural and demand conditions for a model being disseminated, an analysis of the telecommunications and banking market, obstacles to its adoption, gender issues and services. What is now apparent is a scenario that can be regarded as the dawn of an investigation into mobile money and payment. In view of the recent history of this subject-area, this can be expected. Similarly, answers to these questions must be found to ensure that mobile money and payment really takes off, as everybody involved in this market believes it is bound to happen in the near future, and money as we know it today will be largely handled by electronic devices. Moreover, this trend should be welcomed for the sake of social and economic development and to benefit the majority of the population, including the poor.

Therefore, these lessons broadened the knowledge and brought work maturity in me. So, these two months of internship was the time where I got the most exposure to what it is like to work in real life than what was learnt in the classroom. The internship program gave me the experience, which will help to build a platform and prepare for the future.

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Available: ssijmar.in/vol5no3/vol5no3.6.pdf

Questionnaire

Market Survey to study consumer perception towards central trade operation of Nabil Bank Limited:-

Name:

Organization:

Address:

Phone No:

Ques 1: Do you ever visited online shopping.

- Yes
- No

Ques 2: Name Of the online shops and E wallet whose site or App you have visited or used

Ques 3: Since when you have been visiting this site or App.

- 1 year
- 2 year
- 3 year
- More than 3 year

Ques 4: Are you satisfied with trade services provided by the site or App.

- Very much satisfied
- Partially satisfied
- Satisfied
- Not satisfied

Ques 5:

Ques 6: What influenced you to use this site as mediator for trading purpose or will influence you .

- Newspaper
- Word Of Mouth
- Representative From Banks
- Television
- Internet

Ques 7: Which of the following factors attracted you most or will attract you most for using a online site.

- Spending Flexibility
- Perfect for emergencies
- Added benefits
- Status Symbol
- All of the above

Ques 8: Why do you think online shopping is more better than regular one.

Ques 9: Which of the following disadvantages of trade department do you agree with?

- Communication error
- Documentation error
- High interest rates

- all of the above

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The rapid rise in the growth of mobile technology throughout the world is a phenomenon that has been particularly remarkable among poor people, largely because of the prepaid model. As a result, all classes of society now have access to financial services as people become increasingly familiar with a mobile-money system.

In fact, mobile technology, viewed as a payment or banking channel, has the potential to allow two important questions to be addressed at the same time: on the demand side, it represents an opportunity for financial inclusion among a population that is underserved by traditional banking services. On the supply side, it opens up possibilities for financial institutions to deliver a great diversity of services at low cost to a large clientele of the poorest sections of society and people living in remote areas.

Although there are more than 120 mobile money projects being undertaken in about 70 emerging markets (Beshouri et al. 2010), mobile payment has only become a normal practice in a few countries, despite its huge potential

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